

LIMNOLOGY AROUND THE WORLD: POLAND

The Limnological Station of the University of Gdańsk with a Mission to Monitor and Protect Water

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The Limnological Station of the University of Gdańsk was established in 1959 on Raduńskie Górne Lake in upper Radunia River System at the Kashubian Lake District (Fig.1; Lange, 2005). The physical and geographical diversity of the area, *i.e.*, the multitude of morphological forms, lithological diversity of surface sediments, specific climatic and hydrographic conditions make this place a great opportunity to conduct scientific research. The Station also carries out didactic tasks related to field classes in topography, meteorology, geomorphology and hydrology.

Fig. 1 Opening ceremony of the Limnological Station in 1959 (Photo by J. Szukalski)

The Radunia basin, where the Limnological Station is located, is drained by a unique system of cascading lakes, forming the so-called “Raduńskie Lakes Circle” (Fig. 2; Bajkiewicz-Grabowska, 2007). In addition, meteorological observations according to the KLIMAT standard and evaporimetry measurements are also carried out (Miętus, 2006). These data form the basis for the development of climatological maps for Poland for multi-year periods. The maps are also transmitted to the Regional Climatology Centre in Offenbach, Germany. Components of the radiation balance are performed as part of the Polish AOD network (Markowicz *et al.*, 2021).

These unique water resources, along with climate research in collaboration with the Institute of Meteorology and Water Management, are not only valuable scientific data but also educational and training tools. The diverse morphology of these lakes allows a detailed analysis of different types of seasonal and vertical stratification patterns of temperature and oxygen. This and other physio-chemical and biological parameters together with climatic data, all contribute to understanding the factors responsible for lake productivity, rate of organic matter transformation and carbon cycling.

The unfortunate increase in eutrophication in recent years due to climate change and anthropogenic pressure requires a holistic approach to protect these water resources. Lakes are one of the most beautiful gifts of nature, while at the same time presenting a huge challenge to keep them healthy for future generations, requiring close cooperation between all stakeholders. In this

Fig. 2 Map from Bajkiewicz-Grabowska, 2007. Localization of the Limnological Station (LS) at Raduńskie Górne Lake in Radunia Basin (Lakes: 1 - Stężycykie, 2 - Raduńskie Górne, 3 - Raduńskie Dolne, 4 - Rekowo, 5 - Białe, 6 - Kłodno, 7 - Brodno Małe, 8 - Brodno Wielkie, 9 - Lubowisko, 10 - Dąbrowskie, 11 - Patulskie, 12 - Ostrzyckie, 13 - Bukrzyno Małe, 14 - Bukrzyno Wielkie, 15 - Kniewo, 16 - Zamkowisko, 17 - Stare Czaple, 18 - Kamionka, 19 - Sołeckie and 20 - Trzebnio)

situation, the mission of the Limnological Station, in addition to scientific research and educational activities, also needs to support the local community, water managers and politicians in the implementation of innovative monitoring programs.

Fig. 3 Top: Voluntary water monitoring (Photo by R. Głuszewski); bottom: Conference and workshop “What can we do for Kashubian lakes?” organized for local authorities, water managers and the local community (Photo by K. Legeżyńska)

The creation of an integrated and effective educational and training program at the Limnological Station gives a real chance to understand how aquatic ecosystems function, and thus protect them. An important element of the Station’s activity are projects involving the public in Citizen Science initiatives. Starting from voluntary water monitoring with scientists, specialized training, to expert support for the implementation of bottom-up initiatives for the protection and restoration of lakes (Fig. 3).

Fig. 4 Installation of floating islands demonstration

Fig. 5 Applied practical field and laboratory training in ecohydrology for international students. (Photos by J. Dunalska)

The advantage of activities carried out at the Station is not only the possibility of transferring theoretical knowledge, but also its practical application. For this purpose, prototypes of Nature-Based Solutions (NBS) methods used in water protection are being created at the Station (Fig. 4). Demonstrations of individual solutions on a semi-technical and technical scale with additional on-site explanations give great training and educational opportunities for a wide range of stakeholders (school children, students, local government officials, water managers and users).

The uniqueness of the Limnological Station comes from its location and innovative teaching methods both in Polish and English means that it can be an important scientific, educational and training center not only for stakeholders in Poland but also for guests from Europe and the world (Fig. 5). [Find out more here.](#)

References

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*The Limnological Station of the University of Gdańsk on Raduńskie Górne Lake at the Kashubian Lake District.
Photo by Błażej Zablotny.*